

ACTIVE LISTENING: WHAT IS IT

Raximova Laylo Mo'minjanovna

Teacher at Urgench state University

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ANNOTATION

“Active Listening: What is it?” proposes deep explanation of using different listening techniques while teaching EFL and overcoming difficulties occurring while teaching. Using songs and various activities can be an effective method to encourage active learning, and develop their critical-thinking, communication, and decision-making skills of young learners

Key words: critical thinking, interpersonal, uncertainty, thoughtful, concept

Why Is Active Listening Important?

Like critical thinking and problem-solving, active listening is a soft skill that's held in high regard by employers. When interviewing for jobs, using active listening techniques can help show the interviewer how your interpersonal skills can draw people out.

Active listening can also significantly reduce the nervousness you might feel during an interview because it redirects your focus from what is going on inside of your head to the needs of your perspective employer or interviewer. It's a great skill to hone if personal interviews tend to make you a little anxious.

By placing your focus, through active listening, squarely upon the interviewer, you prove that you: a) are interested in the organization's challenges and successes; b) are ready to help them problem-solve work issues, and c) are a team player as opposed to being nothing more than a self-absorbed job candidate.

Listen carefully to the interviewer's questions, ask for clarification if necessary, and wait until the interviewer has finished talking to respond. It's important to not interrupt, or worse, try to answer the question before you know what the interviewer is asking.

Examples of Active Listening

It's often easier to learn by reading examples. Here are some examples of statements and questions employed with active listening:

- Building Trust and Establishing Rapport: “Tell me what I can do to help.” “I was really impressed to read on your website how you donate 5 percent of each sale to charity.”

- Demonstrating Concern: “I am eager to help you; I know you are going through some tough challenges.” “I know how hard a corporate restructuring can be – how is staff morale at this point?”
- Paraphrasing: “So, you are saying that the uncertainty about who will be your new supervisor is creating stress for you.” “So, you think that we need to build up our social media marketing efforts.”
- Brief Verbal Affirmation: “I understand that you would like more frequent feedback about your performance.” “Thank you. I appreciate your time in speaking to me.”
- Asking Open-Ended Questions: “I can see that John's criticism was very upsetting to you. Which aspect of his critique was most disturbing?” “It's clear that the current situation is intolerable for you. What changes would you like to see?”
- Asking Specific Questions: “How long do you expect your hiring process to last?” “What is your average rate of staff turnover?”
- Waiting to Disclose Your Opinion: “Tell me more about your proposal to reorganize the department.” “Can you please provide some history for me regarding your relationship with your former business partner?”
- Disclosing Similar Situations: “I was also very conflicted about returning to work after the birth of my son.” “I had the responsibility of terminating four of my personnel, due to downsizing, over the last two years. Even if it's necessary, it never gets easier.”

By employing these active listening techniques, you will impress your interviewer as a thoughtful, analytical, highly desirable candidate for the position. Think about possible situations that may occur during an interview and come up with strategies to allow you to listen actively.

Improving Your Soft Skills

Never underestimate the power of “soft skills” (also known as “people skills”) like active listening, problem-solving, flexibility, self-motivation, leadership, and teamwork. Your CV or resume may look great, but don't forget to nourish your soft skills.

Especially for young, first-time job candidates with limited work experience, these people skills often are the deciding factor in whether an employer will be willing to take the risk in hiring them over others who may have more experience (but possibly weaker interpersonal communications talents). Don't forget to highlight your soft skills in your interview (and even in your resume).

The nature of listening
'Listening is an active not a passive operation.' Garvie. With this in mind I would like to emphasise three things:

- The importance of understanding this concept of listening being an active engagement. That is, as a listener, the mind is actively searching for meaning.
- The importance of what Krashen calls '*comprehensible input*' (CI) or that 'we acquire when we understand what people tell us or what we read, when we are absorbed in the message.' Individual progress is dependent on the input containing aspects of the target language that 'the acquirer has not yet acquired, but is developmentally ready to acquire.'
 - This seems to imply the importance of ensuring that the language level is matched to the learners, which means teachers must understand their learners' abilities.
- Krashen advises that acquisition proceeds best when 'the acquirer's level of anxiety is low and self-confidence is high.'
 - This seems to enforce the importance of making the learning environment in our classrooms non-threatening.

Why we need to develop listening skills
'If someone is giving you a message or opinion, then of course you have to be able to understand it in order to respond.' (Brewster, Ellis, Girard).

- Listening skills need to have a 'real-life' meaning, Donaldson says that children need 'purposes and intentions' which they can recognise and respond to in others 'these human intentions are the matrix in which the child's thinking is embedded.'
- This implies that we need to carefully select materials and purposes for practising listening skills and that they need to have an authentic meaning to young learners.

Listening skills and young learners

Listening is the receptive use of language, and since the goal is to make sense of the speech, the focus is on meaning rather than language (Cameron 2001). Sariçoban (1999) states that listening is the ability to identify and understand that others are saying. For learners, listening is how spoken language becomes input (i.e., it is the first stage of learning a new language). In the classroom, this happens by listening to the teacher, a CD, or other learners. It is the process of interpreting messages—what people say.

Two theories of speech perception portray listeners as having very different roles. In the first view, listeners play a passive role and simply recognize and decode sounds, and in the second view, listeners play an active role and perceive sounds by accessing internal articulation rules to decode speech (Crystal 1997).

Whether speech perception is active

or passive, or a combination of both, Phillips (1993) says that listening tasks are extremely important in the primary school setting, providing a rich source of language data from which children begin to build up their own ideas of how the foreign language works. This knowledge is a rich source that YLs draw on to produce language. Listening is the initial stage in first and second language acquisition. According to Sharpe (2001), the promotion of children's speaking and listening skills lies at the heart of effective learning in all subjects of the primary curriculum. Therefore, ESL/EFL teachers have to make the development of children's

listening skills a key aim of primary teaching and equip them with the best strategies for effective listening.

Linse (2005) also considers the teaching of listening skills as foundational to the development of other language skills. We should, however, be aware that any kind of listening comprehension activity needs to be well guided with clear aims. To this end, Ur (1996) argues that a listening purpose should be provided in the definition of a pre-set task. The definition of a purpose (a defined goal, as in the "wake up" example) enables the listener to listen selectively for significant information. Providing the students with some idea of what they are going to hear and what they are asked to do with it helps them to succeed in the task; it also raises motivation and interest.

The fact that learners are active during the listening, rather than waiting until the end to do something, keeps the learners busy and helps prevent boredom.

Songs and young learners

The most prominent features of songs that reinforce language acquisition include

their rhythmic and repetitive nature and the joy that the association between melody and content brings to the learning activity. Children have a keen awareness of rhythm, and they have not yet experienced the anxiety that can accompany learning a second language (Krashen 1981). Therefore, songs are considered to be a sine qua non of teaching ESL/EFL to YLs. I feel that among the many advantages of using songs in YL ESL/EFL classrooms, the most striking ones are the following.

Songs are key to primary practice Most primary school teachers generally use songs as a teaching technique, and Cameron (2001) claims that the use of songs and rhymes is also important for YLs in foreign language classrooms. Likewise, Johnstone (2002) claims that teachers of YLs may make an important contribution to children’s early language education by introducing their classes to recorded songs. Demirel (2004) makes the strongest claim when he argues that the most effective way to teach listening comprehension, pronunciation, and dictation to YLs is through teaching songs.

Songs create a safe and natural classroom atmosphere

According to Cullen (1998, 1999), songs are significant teaching tools in teaching ESL/EFL because, as most teachers find out, students love listening to music in the language classroom and they often hold strong views about music. This affinity with music makes songs vital tools to create a safe and natural classroom ethos and to overcome feelings of shyness and hesitation on the part of the learners. Because of their limited attention span, YLs need a variety of activities. YLs are often shy, and they should join in classroom activities when they feel ready rather than when the teacher demands—an opportunity that songs create (Djigunovich and Vilke 2000).

The learning characteristics of YLs also reveal a need to develop a strong emotional attachment to their teacher. Listen and Do songs support this attachment since the students and the teacher are physically involved in doing the same actions; that is, they share a common experience. The students’ education, including language education, is a process in which they should be encouraged to contribute physically, emotionally, and intellectually. This type of learning environment is best achieved when the teacher creates a safe, non-threatening context within which learners can play with language.

Conclusion

Developing listening skills is a fundamental component of any ESL/EFL curriculum for YLs, and songs are regarded as one of the most effective techniques to this end. Songs have a definite place in the YL classroom; they provide meaningful and enjoyable language practice, especially in fostering listening skills. The hope is that the more songs YLs experience, the better language learners they will become.

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